

Multi-period Planning in Metro-Aggregation Networks using Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract—This paper proposes an Integer Linear Programming (ILP) framework to optimize the multi-period planning of metro-aggregation networks exploiting both point-to-multipoint coherent pluggable transceivers and a filterless line system architecture. We investigate several planning strategies to minimize cost while also considering traffic prediction and operational expenditures. The results of a reference network provide evidence of transceiver cost reductions between 20% and 32% compared to the point-to-point approach over a five-year planning period.

Index Terms—point-to-multipoint transceivers, filterless architecture, multi-period planning, integer linear programming

I. INTRODUCTION

Given the significant expenditures associated with deploying and operating metro-aggregation networks, service providers in this segment must carefully consider their technology, architecture, and design options. On the one hand, they want to have stable network operation and minimum capacity upgrades for an extended period of time, hence reducing operational expenditures. On the other hand, they usually prefer to have a pay-as-you-grow investment model, which tends to favor minimizing upfront costs. This can result in conflicting objectives, meaning they have to trade off supporting long-term traffic growth against upfront investments. Successfully striking this trade-off also depends on traffic predictability throughout the network life cycle. Different strategies can be employed to address this problem, taking into account key factors, such as budget limitations and confidence or uncertainty in traffic growth forecast. A comprehensive set of approaches is explained in [1]. Among them, all period

planning [2] and incremental planning [3], [4] are two extreme choices based on considering the demand forecast for all periods or only for the next period, respectively.

Point-to-multipoint (P2MP) coherent pluggable transceivers enabled by digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) hold the promise of better matching the hub-and-spoke traffic pattern in metro-aggregation networks compared to point-to-point (P2P) [5]. In particular, these networks feature a large imbalance between the capacity needed at one or a few central nodes (the hub nodes) and that required in a larger number of distributed nodes (the leaf nodes), where the latter type of nodes only communicate with the former type but not with each other. While traditional P2P solutions rely on pairing transceivers at the hub and leaf nodes, which requires a high number of devices at the hub node, DSCM-based P2MP solutions are able to use a single high-capacity device at the hub node, improving key metrics such as cost, power consumption, and footprint. Recent works have: (i) experimentally demonstrated the feasibility of this technology [6] and (ii) highlighted that the cumulative CAPEX savings, accounting for transceiver cost reductions and further simplifications such as adopting a filterless node architecture [7], could reach 76% over five years when compared to the traditional P2P solution [8]. In our previous work [9], we have analyzed DSCM-based P2MP transceivers under a filterless architecture constraint and assumed generic (i.e., meshed) networks in contrast to regular tree, chain or ring topologies considered in early studies [8]. The results obtained over a reference mesh network show that transceiver costs can be reduced by almost 40% on average [9].

The filterless node architecture efficiently complements the use of DSCM-based P2MP transceivers. Closed loops must be avoided when planning filterless networks to prevent the

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same optical signal from traversing the same link twice [7]. Moreover, pure filterless architectures might not provide dedicated path protection for all node pairs [10] and Inter-Tree Transceivers (ITTs), Colored Passive Filters (CPFs), and red and blue filters (half spectrum blockers) may be required at selected nodes.

Previous works addressed the described scenario focused on a single instance of network design with static traffic and fixed cost figures. However, evaluating the long-term effectiveness of P2MP solutions requires modeling the impact of key factors such as traffic evolution, transceiver cost discounts, and the introduction of higher-capacity transceivers. This work proposes several multiperiod filterless network planning scenarios and a novel framework for the optimal deployment of P2MP transceivers using an ILP model. The suggested model on a reference network architecture shows considerable transceiver savings over the network life cycle.

II. P2MP TRANSCEIVER AND FILTERLESS NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

The DSCM-based P2MP transceivers can communicate with multiple nodes simultaneously. For instance, a 400G P2MP transceiver at the hub node can slice the optical spectrum into 16 subcarriers (SCs) and communicate with a maximum of 16 leaf nodes, providing bidirectional connections of 25G when assuming 16-quadrature amplitude modulation (16QAM) format. Alternatively, it can communicate with, for example, four leaf nodes, each of which assigns a total of four SCs (i.e., 100G). Noteworthy, the transceiver at each leaf node can receive the entire optical signal but only processes its own SCs in the electrical domain. On the reverse path, each leaf node only transmits the SCs that have been assigned to it [11]. This transceiver technology provides an upgrade path that ensures backward compatibility if 4 Gbaud SCs are preserved. Hence, a 800G (1.2T) transceiver of higher capacity will handle a total of 32 (48) SCs [11].

Generally, a higher data rate transceiver provides a better per-bit cost. The cost model of transceivers considered in this work is $Cost = \frac{\sqrt{N_s}}{4}$ where N_s is the number of subcarriers supported. Using this formula, 400G transceivers cost is one unit (normalization of cost to 400G transceiver), and 100G, 800G, and 1.2T transceivers relative prices are 0.5, 1.41, and 1.73, respectively. This model generalizes the approximation that a 4x increase in capacity is achieved at the expense of the doubling cost [8]. Note that other cost profiles can be considered for higher or lower per bit/s cost savings [12].

Filterless architectures are a compelling solution, particularly in network deployments where capacity requirements are not high enough to risk spectrum exhaustion, which is typically the case of metro-aggregation networks [12]. The key benefits of using passive components include a lower cost and a lower probability of failure [7]. A single spanning-tree per direction meets the filterless architecture conditions in networks with a single hub and several leaf nodes. In other words, a spanning tree can connect all leaf nodes to the hub (the root of the tree) without forming any loop. Optical splitters interconnect fibers

upstream, whereas combiners connect fibers downstream to the hub. Fibers can be terminated by either spectrum blockers or directly by transceivers. Figure 1(a) shows a 400G transceiver at the hub communicating with four 100G transceivers located at leaf nodes using a physical tree architecture implemented by combiners and splitters. In this paper, the reference network depicted in Fig. 1 (b) is considered. Note that the location of the hub can affect the cost of P2MP deployment [13]. For simplicity, it is assumed that the node with the shortest paths to all other nodes is the hub.

When adopting a filterless architecture, the tree overlay adopted can influence the total cost of the P2MP (or P2P) solution. For example, its size and shape determine which modulation format may be used, affecting the type and quantity of transceivers required at both the hub and leaf nodes [13]. Also, the tree must be constructed at the beginning of network operation. These insights support simultaneously optimizing the spanning tree and the deployment of P2MP (or P2P) transceivers to achieve the best solution.

III. MULTI PERIOD PLANNING SCENARIOS

Network operators must consistently plan to deploy resources in response to the growing demand for traffic. However, several factors can affect planning, including uncertainty in traffic prediction, technology shifts, and budget limitations. For instance, higher data rate transceivers become available later but offer a per bit/s cost advantage. Moreover, each transceiver generation has a limited lifespan, being discontinued after a number of years because their competitive advantage erodes. This fact, coupled with volume discounts, means that the price of a given transceiver generation gradually decreases during that lifespan. These observations encourage operators to postpone capacity upgrades. However, this approach means more frequent capacity upgrades, increasing operational expenditures, and affecting the quality of service. This work assumes a five-year planning scenario in which 800G and 1.2T transceivers only become available in the market from the second and fourth years, respectively.

Three different multi-period planning scenarios are modeled: (i) all-period planning, (ii) incremental or single-period planning, and (iii) extended-period planning. The all-period planning considers the traffic forecast for all periods and is best suited when there is high confidence in that prediction. Conversely, single-period planning is used when there is low confidence in traffic predictions and/or near-term investments are to be kept to a minimum. Extended-period planning sits in between these extreme cases, assuming that traffic predictions are relatively reliable over three years.

There are two ways to manage leaf node transceivers. One way is to keep a transceiver in place for the rest of the planning period once it's been deployed in a leaf node, which is called the unmovable transceivers strategy in this paper. The other way is to move a transceiver to a different leaf node in the future if it enables reducing CAPEX (movable transceivers). Note that each time a leaf node is upgraded, either by removing or deploying a transceiver or both, it is

Fig. 1. (a) A 400G transceiver deployment at the root of a tree for communicating with four 100G transceivers located at 4 leaf nodes using combiners and splitters, and (b) the considered reference network with 30 nodes and 51 links [14].

necessary to visit the leaf site. Therefore, the chosen approach can affect both CAPEX and OPEX (the latter measured as the number of site visits).

IV. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

This section proposes a novel optimization framework to identify the most cost-effective P2MP transceiver configuration under filterless architecture constraints for a particular planning scenario, network, and traffic load. The main input parameters and decision variables of the ILP model are described below.

Input Parameters

- $G(V, E)$: network graph with nodes $u, i, j \in V$ and links $l = (i, j) \in E$.
- V^- : a subset of V defining leaf nodes.
- W_{ij} : length of link $(i, j) \in E$.
- S : set of planning periods.
- T_u^s : number of 25 Gb/s data rate required by leaf node u in period s . This is assumed to be the maximum required traffic of downstream and upstream directions.
- L_r : maximum reach with highest-order modulation format (16QAM).
- O_h, O_l : sets of transceivers that can be used at the hub and leaf nodes.
- C_o^s : relative cost of transceiver type o in period s .
- D_o : maximum data rate in terms of number of 25G (with the highest modulation format) of transceiver type o .
- B : very large positive number.
- $J(s)$: weighting factor of period s determining the importance of each period.
- $Q(s)$: cost decline parameter for period s .

Decision Variables

- f_{ij} : positive integer variable that indicates the flow from node i to j .
- x_{ij} : 1 if the link $(i, j) \in E$ is selected for the tree, 0 otherwise.
- y_{ij}^u : 1 if edge $(i, j) \in E$ is in the path from leaf u to the hub, 0 otherwise.
- M_{1u} : 1 if the path from leaf u to the hub is longer than L_r (uses QPSK), 0 otherwise.
- M_{2u} : 1 if the path from leaf u to the hub is shorter than L_r (uses 16QAM), 0 otherwise.
- Δ_{1o}^s : cumulative number of transceivers of type o used in period s at the hub with QPSK modulation format.
- Δ'_{1o}^s : positive number indicating the number of transceivers of type o added in period s in the hub with the QPSK modulation format.
- Δ_{2o}^s : cumulative number of transceivers of type o used in period s at the hub with 16QAM modulation format.
- Δ'_{2o}^s : positive number indicating the number of transceivers of type o added in period s in the hub with the 16QAM modulation format.
- δ_{ou}^s : cumulative number of transceivers of type o used in period s at leaf node u .
- δ'_{ou}^s : positive number indicates the number of transceivers of type o added in period s at leaf u .

The objective of the ILP model is to minimize the total transceivers' cost:

$$z = \sum_{s \in S} Q(s) J(s) \left[\sum_{o \in O_h} (\Delta'_{1o}^s + \Delta'_{2o}^s) \times C_o^s + \sum_{u \in V^-} \sum_{o \in O_l} \delta'_{ou}^s \times C_o^s \right], \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in E} x_{ij} = N, \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_j f_{ij}^t - \sum_j f_{ji}^t = \begin{cases} N & i = Hub, \\ -1 & \forall i \in V^-, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$f_{ij} \leq Nx_{ij} \quad \forall (i, j) \in E, \quad (4)$$

$$f_{ji} \leq Nx_{ij} \quad \forall (i, j) \in E, \quad (5)$$

$$BM_{1u} \geq \sum_{(i,j) \in E} W_{ij} y_{ij}^u - L_r \quad \forall u \in V^-, \quad (6)$$

$$M_{1u} + M_{2u} = 1 \quad \forall u \in V^-, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{o \in O_l} \delta_{ou}^s D_o \leq T_u [M_{1u} + 1] \quad \forall u \in V^-, \forall s \in S, \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{o \in O_h} \Delta_{1o}^s D_o \geq \sum_{u \in V^-} 2T_u M_{1u} \quad \forall s \in S, \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{o \in O_h} \Delta_{2o}^s D_o \geq \sum_{u \in V^-} T_u M_{2u} \quad \forall s \in S, \quad (10)$$

$$\delta'_{ou} = \delta_{ou}^s - \delta_{ou}^{s-1} \quad \forall u \in V^-, \forall o \in O_l, \forall s \in S, \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta'_{1o} = \Delta_{1o}^s - \Delta_{1o}^{s-1} \quad \forall o \in O_h, \forall s \in S, \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta'_{2o} = \Delta_{2o}^s - \Delta_{2o}^{s-1} \quad \forall o \in O_h, \forall s \in S. \quad (13)$$

Constraint (2) ensures that the size of the tree is equal to the number of leaf nodes N (assuming all leaf nodes have to be connected to the hub). According to constraint (3), N units of flow are distributed by the hub node, and all N leaf nodes receive precisely one unit of flow. Flows can only be on trees that do not exceed the total number of flows by constraints (4–5). These conditions create a spanning tree by fulfilling the criteria of the tree through a single commodity approach [15]. We consider that the quadrature phase-shift keying (QPSK) modulation format is feasible for paths longer than $L_r = 500$ km, while for paths shorter than that, 16QAM can be used. Note that using QPSK instead of 16QAM halves the capacity per SC. Constraints (6) and (7) specify if QPSK or 16QAM modulation format can be used. M_{1u} (M_{2u}) takes the value of 1 if the path to the leaf node requires the QPSK (16QAM) modulation format. Note that it is assumed that all SCs transmitted/received by a transceiver must use the same modulation format. Constraints (8–10) measure the cumulative number of required transceivers while constraints (11–13) count the number of transceivers added in period s per type at the leaf and hub nodes according to the modulation format selected.

The scenario of movable transceivers can be implemented by adding Eq. (14) to the set of constraints and letting δ'_{ou}^s take both positive and negative integer values, allowing to increase or decrease the number of transceivers of a given type at each leaf node.

$$\sum_{u \in V^-} \delta'_{ou}^s = \left[\sum_{u \in V^-} (\delta_{ou}^s - \delta_{ou}^{s-1}) \right] \geq 0 \quad \forall o \in O_l, \forall s, \quad (14)$$

The ILP model can also be modified to design the network with P2P transceivers. In this case, the leaf and hub nodes must have transceiver pairs that operate at the same data rate. Therefore, we can model it by removing the first term of the objective function (1) and doubling the second term of this function.

Table I presents the baseline cost matrix for all transceivers considered in this study. A very high value (e.g., 1000) is used in the ILP formulation when a transceiver is not available.

TABLE I
RELATIVE TRANSCIVER COST PER DATA RATE BY YEAR WITHOUT
CONSIDERING COST DISCOUNT

	100G	400G	800G	1.2T
Year 1	0.5	1	Unavailable	Unavailable
Year 2	0.5	1	1.41	Unavailable
Year 3	0.5	1	1.41	Unavailable
Year 4	0.5	1	1.41	1.73
Year 5	0.5	1	1.41	1.73

The weighting factor $J(s)$ is introduced in the objective function (Eq. 1) to model the relevance of each planning period in the CAPEX optimization. For instance, if $J(s)$ takes a much larger number for a given year with respect to that for the remaining years (e.g., first year), then the model will give preference to minimizing CAPEX in that particular year.

As explained earlier and given pricing policies such as customer-driven pricing, price skimming, and premium pricing, transceivers' cost usually declines after they reach the market. We considered a 10% reduction per year after they become available in the market by setting the cost decline to $Q(s) = 0.9^{s-1}$ in Eq. 1, where s varies from 1 to 5.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section examines the performance of DSCM-based P2MP transceivers during a five-year planning period considering the metro-aggregation reference network depicted in Fig. 1(b).

An initial traffic pattern is generated using a Poisson distribution with a 100G mean. The annual growth rate is set as a random number between 25% and 35% for each leaf node. In the following, we express the average traffic load per leaf node in multiples of 25G to facilitate interpretation of the results. All of the results are the average value of 10 independent Monte-Carlo simulations.

Figure 2(a) shows the cumulative transceiver cost for the three different scenarios discussed in section III. It can be observed that with all-period planning, the initial cost is higher, but the cost increase is smoother, leading to the lowest cost in the final periods. This is expected because this strategy gives preference to minimizing the total CAPEX, even if that entails a less optimal solution in the first periods (e.g., due to transceiver underutilization). The extended-period planning and single-period planning result in similar cost in the first two years. However, single-period planning becomes less cost-effective with time due to decisions that are not optimal in the long run. Interestingly, extended-period planning performs

Fig. 2. (a) P2MP transceiver cost for all-period, extended-period and single-period planning, and (b) the amount of savings compared to the corresponding P2P transceiver approaches.

better or as well as all-period planning up to the third period, only leading to a higher cumulative cost than all-period planning in the last two periods.

Figure 2(b) plots the cost savings obtained with P2MP versus P2P unmovable transceivers. Note that for the P2P scenario, the traffic requirements between the hub and a single leaf only justify using 100G and 400G data rates. In general, the amount of savings is between 20% and 32% for all different planning strategies. The all-period P2P planning initially deploys a larger number of 400G transceivers, so there is less need to upgrade transceivers in the following years. This explains the higher at the beginning and lower savings at the end of the planning period. The degree of savings obtained with the other two planning strategies is less dependent on the planning years. It is noteworthy that P2MP transceivers grant higher cost savings at the end of five years when single-period planning is adopted.

The next set of results evaluates the impact of being able to move transceivers among leaf nodes. Figure 3(a) shows the cost reduction of the P2MP movable transceiver approach compared to the non-movable one. Moreover, an OPEX-related metric – the number of site visits to deploy/swap transceivers – is depicted in Fig. 3(b). As can be seen, allowing transceivers to be moved between leaf nodes decreases the cost of all-period planning by about 13% at the beginning (less over-provisioning compared to the unmovable transceivers),

Fig. 3. (a) Cost reduction of the movable transceiver approach compared to unmovable transceivers for different planning strategies and (b) their number of visits to the leaf nodes.

but there are no significant improvements for the next four years. However, this early CAPEX reduction is achieved at the expense of increasing the number of site visits from 44 to 78 (77% increase). The range of improvement for extended-period and single-period planning is considerable in the last planning periods. Regarding extended-period planning, CAPEX is reduced by about 12% while OPEX increases by around 8% compared to the unmovable transceiver approach. For the single-period planning method, not only is CAPEX decreased by almost 14% but OPEX is slightly reduced. When comparing the three scenarios, it is clear that single-period planning always involves more site visits, followed by extended-period planning, whereas all-period planning demands fewer visits (benefit of adopting higher data rate transceivers early on).

In order to gain further insight, Table II shows the number of transceivers deployed per type for one of the traffic load sets in the single-period planning strategy. In the first and the second year, both unmovable and movable transceivers' strategies deploy the same amount of transceivers. However, with increased traffic in the following years, the unmovable transceivers strategy continues to add several new 100G transceivers. On the contrary, the movable transceivers approach relocates existing transceivers (the number of displaced transceivers is shown in parentheses) between leaf nodes, especially 100G transceivers. Therefore, the low data rate transceiver count can be limited by enabling transceiver reuse even if only next year's traffic is

TABLE II
NUMBER OF TRANSCEIVERS ADDED PER TYPE AT LEAF NODES IN UNMOVABLE AND MOVABLE TRANSCEIVERS APPROACHES.

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
Unmovable Transceivers	44×100G	14×100G	13×100G	22×100G	34×100G
Movable Transceivers	44×100G	14×100G	5×400G (8×100G)	5×400G (2×400G+18×100G)	8×400G (5×400G+36×100G)

predicted. In summary, in cases where the traffic prediction is for all five years, all-period planning can deliver the minimum transceiver cost and the fewest number of leaf visits at the end of the 5-year planning period. However, the movable transceivers approach allows significantly reducing transceiver cost when accurate traffic prediction is limited, and extended-period or single-period planning is adopted instead.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper described a novel ILP model for multi-period planning in metro-aggregation networks using P2MP (or P2P) transceivers and filterless node architecture. The cost of supporting all traffic demands using P2MP transceivers was compared to that of utilizing traditional P2P transceivers in a reference network topology over a five-year planning period. The results show that significant cost savings can be achieved, ranging from 20% to almost 32%, depending on the planning strategy. Our work suggests that in case of lack of confidence in traffic prediction, it is efficient in terms of CAPEX to exploit transceiver relocation. Future work will extend the analysis by including a more detailed joint CAPEX and OPEX analysis.

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